

THE FORMATION OF COGNITIVE-VISUAL SKILLS IN THE ACTIVITIES OF TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This article provides a reference to the formation of cognitive and visual skills in the activities of teachers, the importance of cognitive and visual skills and their role in human life.

Modern education in the 21st century. will be more flexible, open, dynamic. It includes new pedagogical technologies, educational practices and concepts. The criteria of professional skills of future pedagogues, the problems of creating an innovative educational environment in the research conducted by the world's leading higher education institutions and scientific centers on innovative training of future specialists, implementation of modern education, international education special importance is attached to the introduction of the requirements of lim standards. An important place in this is occupied by scientific research aimed at expanding the structure of the pedagogical competence of young teachers on the basis of such indicators as motivational, cognitive, operational, reflexive and self-assessment of the successful application of modern information and pedagogical technologies in the educational process.

The pedagogical process is a complex systemic phenomenon. The high importance of the pedagogical process is due to the cultural, historical and social significance of the process of maturation of the individual. In this regard, it is very important to understand the main peculiarities of the pedagogical process, to know what tools are needed for its most effective flow. Many domestic and foreign specialists, pedagogical scientists, psychologists are engaged in the study of this problem. Cognitive psychology is one of the most popular scientific areas of foreign psychology. Translated into Russian, the term "cognitive" means cognitive. This line of research was formed mainly in the 1960s, the results of the first stage of its development were published in 1967 V. Summarized in the monograph "Cognitive Psychology" by Naiser, he gave the name to a new direction of psychological thought. R. In a later book with the same name, Solso writes that cognitive psychology studies how people perceive information about the world, how this information is expressed by a person, how it is stored in memory, transformed into knowledge, and how it is. Knowledge affects our attention and behavior.

Thus, almost all cognitive processes are covered - from sensations to perception, pattern recognition, memory, concept formation, thinking, imagination. The main areas of cognitive psychology that have been common in many countries for several decades usually include research on the problems of Developmental Psychology of cognitive structures, the psychology of language and speech, the development of cognitive theories.

Thus, cognitive psychology is based on a person's idea as a system that deals with the search for information about objects and phenomena in the surrounding world, as well as the processing and storage of incoming information. At the same time, individual cognitive processes provide for the implementation of various stages of information processing.

The concept of cognitive-visual activity entered the field of education as a result of scientific research by pedagogical - psychologist researchers. From a psychological point of view, Cognitive - the term denoting the ability of a person to mentally perceive and process external information, refers to how, in unexpected cases, a specialist behaves, behaves in a new way in interaction with colleagues, performs ambiguous tasks, uses information full of conflicts, owns a plan of movement in consistently developing and complex processes.

The cognitive-visual process is a direction in psychology, according to which individuals not only have a mechanical effect on external phenomena or internal factors, but also use the power of reason for this. His theoretical approach is to understand how thinking is arranged, how incoming information is solved, and how it is organized to make decisions or perform everyday tasks.

Cognitive-visual means, in one way or another, are associated with cognition, thinking, ensure the acquisition of consciousness and functions of the brain, input knowledge and information, the formation of concepts and their functioning.

Cognitive activity is understood as a person's ability to process thoughts. It is "the ability of an individual to perform various mental actions that are closely related to learning and problem solving. For example, verbal, spatial, psychomotor and processing speed skills". Perception mainly refers to things like memory, speech and the ability to learn new information. The brain is usually able to learn new skills and develop personal thoughts and beliefs about the world in the areas mentioned above, usually in early childhood. Old age and illness can affect cognitive functioning memory loss and the appearance of problems when thinking the right words while speaking or writing Cant. Multiple sclerosis for example can eventually lead to memory loss, inability to understand new concepts or information, and decreased verbal fluency.

People usually have higher opportunities for cognitive activity after birth, so almost every person has the ability to learn or remember. The mind is tested with IQ tests and others, although there are problems with their accuracy and completeness. In such tests, people can be asked a series of questions or complete tasks, each measuring cognitive abilities such as consciousness, memory, awareness, problem solving, motor skills, analytical skills, or other similar concepts. Studies are related to the cognitive activity of the human being and cognitivism is based on that mental activity, not behavior.

Cognitive tools, in one way or another, are associated with cognition, thinking, ensure the acquisition of consciousness and functions of the brain, input knowledge and information, the formation of concepts and their functioning. Cognitive activity is studied by psychologists

and educators from different angles, but any study is considered as part of the general problem of education and development. All efforts will focus on improving the educational process.

Cognitive functions, cognitive skills or cognitive capabilities, called cognitive skills, are brain-based skills needed to acquire knowledge, manipulate information, and reason. They are more related not to the knowledge of people, but to the mechanisms of learning, remembering, solving problems and paying attention. Cognitive skills or functions encompass domains perception, attention, memory, learning, decision-making and language manifested by the development of abilities.

The problem of the formation of cognitive activity of students in the educational process is one of the most important in modern pedagogical science, because improving the quality of education, encouraging students to achieve educational and creative results largely depends on its solution. The solution to such problems is considered to further improve the potential of pedagogical personnel, expand their capabilities, become strong both mentally and physically.

The spiritual perfection of the teacher, a strong self-confident character, the ability to find a solution to any problem and solve it, is a requirement of today. Summarizing these, we can say that cognitive-visual skills are called, and in the activities of teachers it is necessary to introduce, develop this process. In order to develop the cognitive-visual characteristics of teachers, a lot of pedagogical and psychological work has been carried out, and the very fact that it has been studied by many scientists shows to what extent this is important.

In place of the conclusion, it can be said that the pedagogical process is a developing interaction of educators and educators aimed at achieving a certain goal and leading to a pre-planned change in the situation, a change in the characteristics and qualities of the teacher. In other words, the pedagogical process is the process by which social experience is absorbed into individual qualities. In this process, a huge amount of knowledge, experience, qualifications are required from the educator. The same cognitive-visual skills. Since a preliminary assessment of the situation, a comprehensive study of problems, regulation of the flow of a large amount of information in one's own mind, the ability to achieve commonality in thoughts and actions is a necessary factor for the teacher, the development and learning of cognitive-visual skills will remain relevant.

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